

The Need for The Development of Canva-Assisted Animated Video Learning Media in The Cultivation and Development of Honest Attitudes in Pancasila Education in Elementary Schools

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ABSTRACT: Honest attitude becomes the focus in the development of learning at school age and becomes a character that is in accordance with the values of Pancasila. The purpose of this study was to determine the level of needs of students and teachers on canva-assisted animated video learning media in the cultivation and development of honest attitudes. The type of research is descriptive qualitative with research subjects of elementary school students and teachers in Mojosoongo sub-district. The instrument used is a questionnaire, with the indicator being the need for canva-assisted animated video learning media in supporting the cultivation and development of honest attitudes. The results showed that: 1) 100% concluded that learning to cultivate and develop honest attitudes at this time with the lecture method and not using Canva assistance; 2) 100% concluded that it is necessary to develop learning to cultivate and develop honest attitudes with media using Canva-assisted media because it has space to interpret its meanings; 3) 100% concluded that it is necessary to develop learning to cultivate and develop honest attitudes using Canva-assisted media because it can develop interaction; 4) 100% concluded that teachers and students agree to develop learning to cultivate and develop honest attitudes using Canva-assisted media. Based on the results of the questionnaire analysis, it can be concluded that it is necessary to develop Canva-assisted animated video learning media in Pancasila Education for the cultivation and development of honest attitudes.

KEYWORDS: Canva, honest attitude, learning media.

INTRODUCTION

Pancasila education at the elementary school level has a strategic role in shaping the character of the younger generation based on the noble values of the nation. Kandia, et al, (2023) explained that the progress of a country depends on its National Education system. Improving the quality of education is the main target of development in the field of national education and is an integral part of efforts to improve the quality of Indonesian human beings. This is also confirmed by Santika and Suastika (2022) that a person can be said to have succeeded in education, if after participating in learning students are able to show positive changes in thinking abilities, skills, and attitudes. This explanation can be interpreted that a person can be said to have succeeded in education, if after participating in learning students are able to show positive changes in thinking abilities, skills, and attitudes.

One of the focuses of the research is the development of honest attitudes in students. The development of honest attitudes in students is part of character development. This character development needs to start since learners are at a young age, one of which is in elementary school education. Baehr (2017) explains that at school age, children are at a critical phase of development where they begin to learn to understand the difference between right and wrong. This explanation directs that character education needs to be implemented at the elementary level because it can help guide learners in understanding the importance of moral values, such as: honesty, respect, responsibility, and cooperation.

The development of honesty in students needs to be done systematically and apply learning and learning theories in every subject in elementary school. Shofwan (2021) explains that there are four main reasons for developing honesty in elementary school, namely: 1) elementary school age is a sensitive period in which children's physical, motor, intellectual, and social development takes place rapidly; 2) 50% of adult intelligence is formed in the first four years of life, with an additional 30% formed up to the age of eight; 3) the school period is the initial foundation for children's growth and development, making it a crucial moment to instill educational values that will affect children's development in the future; and 4) Character education is very appropriate to be applied in early childhood because at this stage, children are still relatively free from negative influences from the external environment.

Considering the above description, the cultivation and development of honesty in elementary school is an ideal period and a necessity to instill positive values that can shape children's character in the future.

Subjects in elementary school that are aligned and focused on cultivating and developing an attitude of honesty are Pancasila Education. This subject focuses on education about morals as an Indonesian nation which aims to form good citizens, understand the rights and obligations of citizenship, love the country, and have an Indonesian national spirit. Akhyar and Dewi (2022) explain that in the context of basic education, the cultivation of Pancasila values such as honesty is a basic aspect that must be strengthened in the subject. Being honest is a very important character and must exist in humans, because being honest makes us a valuable person (Akhyar and Dewi 2022). Based on the importance of honesty for humans, cultivating an honest attitude for students is not only a moral value but also a foundation in building students to be responsible and fair in their lives.

Attitude is a response shown by students to educators when learning takes place. Damiaty, et al. (2017: 36), explain that attitude is an expression of a person's feelings that reflect his liking or dislike of an object. Setyowati and Rina Insani (2023) explain that attitude is an individual consciousness that determines real or possible actions in social social activities. Noting this description, the notion of attitude can also be described as the way a person sees something mentally that leads to behavior shown to other people, ideas, objects, or certain groups.

According to Myers (Sancaya & Arofah, 2022) attitudes are formed through personal experience, social influence, and the media. These attitudes then influence a person's social behavior, although there are times when a person's behavior does not fully reflect the attitudes they have due to the influence of other factors such as social norms or external pressures. In addition, attitude change is also a focus in his book. Myers (Sancaya & Arofah, 2022) discusses various theories of attitude change, such as persuasion theory which explains how information or messages received can change a person's attitude. Factors such as source credibility, message appeal, and an individual's ability to process information play a major role in attitude change. Overall, Myers emphasizes that attitudes are not fixed and can change over time through interaction with the social environment or new information.

Attitudes reflect a person's psyche and the way they communicate feelings to others. Damiaty (2017: 39) explains that attitudes can be shaped, influenced and changed by experience, information and social factors Although behaviors do not always reflect the attitudes held, due to external factors such as social norms or pressure, attitudes still influence the way a person acts. Attitudes consist of cognitive (thinking), affective (feeling), and conative (desire to act), affective (feelings), and conative (desire to act), which can change over time through experience, social interaction, or new information. Based on this description, Sherif (Supeni, Hakim, & Jumintono, 2019) explains that the characteristics of attitudes are: 1) Attitude is not a factor of heredity or not carried by humans from birth, but is formed and learned along with the development of life that occurs in humans in relation to objects; 2) The nature of the non-heredity, then the attitude can change if the conditions that can support the change are there, because it changes then the attitude can be learned by people or vice versa; 3) Attitude does not solely stand alone but is always related to the object, or in other words the attitude is formed, learned or changed always with respect to a particular object; 4) The object of attitude is not only one particular thing, but can also be a collection of these things, or in other words, the object contained in the attitude is not only one but also with respect to a series of similar objects; 5) In attitudes generally have a motivational and emotional aspect or feeling, this trait is what distinguishes between attitudes with skills or knowledge that a person has.

The word honest is the root word of honesty which means straightforward; not lying (e.g. telling the truth); not cheating (e.g. in a game following the rules that apply); sincere; sincere. Honest in speech means that every word that comes out of one's mouth should contain or contain the values of truth and honesty (Amin, 2017). While another understanding of honesty is the truthfulness of one's speech and in accordance with what happens. A person's honest attitude lies in what is said and what is done (Karviandi, 2020). An honest attitude is a trait that requires a person to say and do according to what is really true, nothing is hidden, and there is no personal interest that covers the truth (Shihab, 2002). From the above description, it can be synthesized that an honest attitude can be concluded that an honest attitude is a trait that requires a person to speak and act in accordance with reality, without hiding the truth or any personal interests that cover it.

Facts in the field show that the development of character values in elementary schools (SD) focuses on the development of the cognitive domain. That is, students understand the meaning of honesty and the characteristics of students have character values about honesty. This is indicated by data from observations at elementary schools in Mojosoongo sub-district, Boyolali district on Tuesday, November 12 to Thursday, December 12, 2024, obtained data that: students are able to define the meaning of honesty and the characteristics of individuals having honest character; and the test results obtained data on the lowest score of 75, the highest

score of 100, the average of 87.25, and standard deviation 7.251. but when asked about how to do homework, 21 out of 24 students stated that they did it themselves and 3 students stated that they were helped and done by the students' parents. this shows that there is a contrast in education, namely the cognitive domain is better than the development of the attitude domain.

The implementation of the value of honesty in learning often faces challenges. Based on initial observations in elementary schools, learning methods through Pancasila Education lessons used still tend to be conventional, such as lectures containing honesty material and giving assignments that still focus on cognitive development. This, of course, makes the development of the attitude domain less than optimal. The habituation method for instilling the value of honesty does not get enough portion. This is because 29 out of 36 teachers, from the results of interviews about methods of cultivating honesty, provide an explanation of the definition of honesty and examples that exist at school and in the community. These examples, such as: not cheating on friends' answers during tests, if told by parents and there is change for the money, then hand it back. This method tends to provide cognitive understanding but the application is not able to go deep. While 7 out of 36 teachers in explaining honest attitudes through reading in the Pancasila Education book. The results of the teacher's reading ask to give students to comment. The method of the 7 teachers leads to problem-based learning. However, the problems given by the teacher are still limited to the context that does not touch the attitude of students.

The cultivation and development of attitudes for students in elementary schools needs to be given material that can be analyzed and synthesized through the observation method. One of the ways to support learning with the observation method is to develop learning media that contains attitude development activities. Nurhalimah and Azzahra (2023) explain that learning media are all forms of physical equipment designed in a planned manner to convey information and build interaction. The physical equipment includes original objects, printed materials, visuals, audio, audio visuals, multimedia and the web. Widiyanto, Rahmatiah, Baso, Lestari, and Arifin (2022) explain that learning media is a tool that can be used to help the learning process to be more effective and optimal. Based on the description above, researchers can conclude that learning media are all means in printed or electronic form that can be used to assist learning for educators and students in achieving learning goals.

Learning media that are aligned with the learning styles of elementary school students and the existence of software support for teachers, namely Canva-based learning media. Nurhalimah, & Azzahra (2023) explained that one form of learning media that is increasingly relevant in the digital era is animated video-based media. Animated videos are visual media that combine elements of images, text, sound, and animation to convey certain information or messages. Canva helps provide easy services for educators and students related to the creation of educational content with a stable internet connection and devices that can be used from a laptop, pc or via cellphone (Citradevi, 2023). Canva, as a user-friendly graphic design platform, provides various features that can be used to create animated videos easily and creatively (Fatimah, 2024). Meanwhile, Churiyah, Basuki, Dharma, Filianti, & Sakdiyyah (2022) explain that Canva is an online graphic design platform that allows users to create various types of designs intuitively and easily. The explanation above can be interpreted that Canva is an online graphic design platform that allows users to create various types of designs intuitively and easily. Based on the descriptions above, researchers can synthesize that Canva-based learning media is a tool in electronic form that uses an online graphic design platform, namely Canva, which is used to create various types of designs intuitively and easily.

An interesting and interactive learning medium for elementary school students is animated videos. In this context, the Canva platform is a popular choice for producing animated videos that are easy to make but still professional. Churiyah, Basuki, Dharma, Filianti, & Sakdiyyah (2022) explained that Canva-based animated video media was chosen by considering the following: 1) Attractive Visuals: Dynamic visual elements are able to attract learners' attention and maintain concentration longer; 2) Interactivity: Animated videos can be designed to engage learners through interactive elements such as questions or challenges during playback; 3) Improves Concept Understanding: The use of images and animation allows visualization of abstract concepts to become concrete; 4) Provides a Multisensory Learning Experience: The combination of visuals, text, and audio helps learners learn through multiple senses, improving information retention.

Based on the description above, this study can formulate the formulation of the problem, namely how is the need for the development of Canva-assisted learning media on the material of planting and developing honest attitudes in Boyolali sub-district? This study aims to determine the level of need for the development of Canva-assisted learning media on the material of planting and developing honest attitudes in Pancasila Education lessons.

RESEARCH METHODS

This research is qualitative research. Sugiyono (2022: 19) qualitative research is a research method used to research on natural object conditions, and the researcher himself as the key instrument. The research subjects in this study were grade IV students and elementary school teachers in Ngemplak Boyolali sub-district. The data collection technique uses a questionnaire, with indicators in the form of the need for Canva-based learning media facilities. Analyze the questionnaire using the percentage formula, which is formulated:

$$Percentage = \frac{Multiple\ Subject\ Answers}{Many\ Subjects} \times 100\%$$

The percentage value is greater than 80, so it is interpreted that Canva-based learning media can be developed to the design and development stages.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data collection through a questionnaire with the subject of 20 teachers in Boyolali sub-district, Central Java, Indonesia, focused on the need for learning to cultivate and develop honest attitudes through Canva-assisted media. The results of the data acquisition are compiled in the table below:

Table 1. Summary of Teacher Needs Analysis Questionnaire on Learning to Cultivate and Develop Honest Attitudes Using Canva

No.	Question	Number of “Yes” Answers	Percentage
1	Has there been any learning to instill honest attitudes using Canva for students?	0	0%
2	Do teachers experience problems with learning to instill and develop honest attitudes through lectures?	20	100%
3	Is the learning to instill and develop honest attitudes used by teachers sufficient to support this learning?	1	5%
4	Can learning to instill and develop honest attitudes using the lecture method accommodate the habituation and understanding of honest attitudes?	2	10%
5	Does learning to instill and develop honest attitudes using Canva make it easier for students to build honest attitudes?	18	90%
6	Is it necessary to develop learning to instill and develop honest attitudes with Canva-assisted media to develop students' honest attitudes?	20	100%
7	Do teachers know about learning to instill and develop honest attitudes with Canva-assisted media?	10	50%
8	Have you ever used learning to instill and develop honest attitudes using Canva-assisted media?	3	15%
9	Is it necessary to develop learning to instill and develop honest attitudes with media using Canva-assisted media?	20	100%
10	Does learning to instill and develop an honest attitude using Canva-assisted media provide space for interpreting its meanings?	20	100%

The results of the summary of the questionnaire analysis of students' needs for learning media for planting and developing honest attitudes assisted by Canva, are arranged in the table as follows:

Table 2. Summary of Questionnaire Analysis of Learners' Needs for Cultivation and Development of Honest Attitudes Assisted by Canva

No.	Question	Number of "Yes" Answers	Percentage
A. Learning media needs			
1	Have students ever seen learning media for planting and developing honest attitudes using Canva-assisted media?	15	10%
2	Have students ever been taught to plant and develop honest attitudes using Canva-assisted media?	0	0%
3	Do students have student worksheets (LKPD) with material on planting and developing honest attitudes?	150	100%
4	Have teachers ever taught planting and developing honest attitudes using Canva-assisted media?	0	0%
5	In planting and developing honest attitudes using LKPD media, do teachers ask to work on practice questions continuously and give homework assignments?	150	100%
6	In planting and developing honest attitudes, do teachers use a lecture learning model?	150	100%
7	Is the model of planting and developing honest attitudes with lecture and group methods, can students understand the learning material?	25	37.50%
8	Do teachers always use conventional learning (lectures, asking, giving assignments) and in groups?	140	93.33%
B. Learning Needs for Cultivating and Developing Honest Attitudes Using Canva-Assisted Media			
1	Can learning to instill and develop honest attitudes using Canva-assisted media be done by students?	150	100%
2	Does learning to instill and develop honest attitudes using Canva-assisted media provide benefits to students?	150	100%
3	Do students enjoy learning to instill and develop honest attitudes using Canva-assisted media?	150	100%
4	Can students help each other in interpreting the instillation and development of honest attitudes using Canva-assisted media?	128	85.33%
5	Do students want to learn to instill and develop honest attitudes using Canva-assisted media?	150	100%
6	Can communication between students in learning to instill and develop honest attitudes using Canva-assisted media run optimally?	150	100%
7	Can learning to instill and develop honest attitudes using Canva-assisted media foster learning motivation in students?	150	100%
8	Can the question material presented in implementing learning to instill and develop honest attitudes using Canva-assisted media be understood by students?	150	100%
9	Do students agree that there is learning to instill and develop honest attitudes using media assisted by Canva?	150	100%
C. Learning Needs for Cultivating and Developing Honest Attitudes Using Canva-Assisted Media			
	Learning to instill and develop an honest attitude using Canva-assisted media is one way to analyze and synthesize the values of social activities in society. Interaction events in society are arranged in		

	the form of fragments for the development of an honest attitude. Through fragments arranged in videos assisted by Canva, references and contradictory values are provided.		
1	Based on the explanation above, learning to instill and develop honest attitudes using Canva-assisted media provides space for students to try, understand the meaning, and interpret the values of honest attitudes?	150	100%
2	Can learning to cultivate and develop honest attitudes using Canva-assisted media build social communication between students?	150	100%
3	Do students agree that learning to cultivate and develop honest attitudes uses Canva-assisted media?	150	100%

The results of the summary of the questionnaire analysis of students' needs for learning media for cultivating and developing honest attitudes using Canva-assisted media can be described as follows: 1) 100% concluded that learning the cultivation and development of honest attitudes with the lecture method and not using Canva assisted media; 2) 100% concluded that it is necessary to develop learning to cultivate and develop honest attitudes with media using Canva-assisted media because it has space to interpret its meanings; 3) 100% concluded that learning to cultivate and develop honest attitudes using Canva-assisted media because it can interact and interpret the meaning of honest attitude values; 4) 100% concluded that teachers and students agree to develop learning to cultivate and develop honest attitudes using Canva-assisted media.

DISCUSSION

The development of Canva-assisted learning media provides an opportunity to be developed in learning Pancasila education. This is because Canva-assisted learning media can accommodate social activities that occur in the community and need to be observed for social values, such as honesty. This is because Canva as a user-friendly graphic design platform, provides various features that can be used to create animated videos easily and creatively (Fatimah, 2024). The utilization of Canva by educators is because it can develop animated video-based learning media that are not only informative but also aesthetic, thus supporting a more effective and enjoyable learning process. This observation provides opportunities for interaction between students and teachers and between students. this is in accordance with the concept of Nurhalimah and Azzahra (2023) explaining that learning media are all forms of physical equipment designed in a planned manner to convey information and build interaction. The physical equipment includes original objects, printed materials, visuals, audio, audio visuals, multimedia and the web. This explanation emphasizes that learning media, one of which is Canva-assisted learning media, can build interaction.

The interaction in the utilization of Canva-assisted learning media makes Pancasila education learning more effective. This effectiveness is the cultivation and development of an honest attitude through the results of analysis and synthesis of a fragment of events in society. The emergence of this interaction emphasizes that Canva media is able to be oriented to teachers and students. It is explained that Canva media is user-oriented. Due to its simple yet functional features, Canva helps teachers and students produce quality videos without requiring high technical skills (Widayati et.al, 2023). The ability of Canva-assisted learning media is in line with the statement from Widiyanto, Rahmatiah, Baso, Lestari, and Arifin (2022) explaining that learning media is a tool that can be used to help the learning process to be more effective and optimal. The explanation emphasizes that learning media is a tool that can be used to help the learning process to be more effective and optimal. Effectiveness and optimization in this case are students building attitudes through understanding concepts that are in accordance with their learning style.

The selection of Canva-assisted learning media needs to be developed in learning to cultivate and develop honest attitudes because it is able to motivate students' learning in building concepts, skills, and attitudes, the material can be understood according to the learning style of students, and create interaction in learning. This is in line with the concept explained by Wahyuni (2020) that the functions of learning media, namely: 1) arouse motivation for the spirit of learning where students become more interested in learning which was previously saturated with monotonous learning to become exciting learning because of the learning media; 2) review the material that has been learned so that students do not forget the previous material; 3) provide learning stimulus students are given stimuli as a way to make students think more about high curiosity; 4) activate the response of students to be active in the

classroom; 5) The teacher provides feedback through questions in order to find out students in understanding the material and there needs to be a follow-up if there is a mistake, so that the educator is obliged to correct students' misunderstandings in understanding the material; 6) Hold appropriate exercises or evaluation assessments.

Learning media for the cultivation and development of honest attitudes are requested to be developed because they provide benefits for students and teachers. This is because Canva-assisted learning media is able to accommodate fragments of social events that exist in the community, build interaction between students, be more effective and efficient in learning, and improve the quality of learning outcomes for students. this is in accordance with the concept explained by Widiyanto, Rahmatiah, Baso, Lestari, and Arifin (2022) that the benefits of learning media, namely: 1) The delivery of subject matter can be uniformed; 2) The learning process becomes clearer and more interesting; 3) The learning process becomes more interactive; 4) Efficiency in time and energy; 5) Improve the quality of student learning outcomes; 6) The media allows the learning process to be carried out anywhere and anytime; 7) Media can foster a positive attitude of students towards the material and the learning process; 8) Change the role of educators in a more positive and productive direction.

The need for planting and developing an honest attitude using Canva-assisted learning media needs to be developed because it fulfills the aspects and indicators of development. Indah et al., (2024) explain that the aspects and indicators of Audio Visual Media Development include: 1) aspects of feasibility, including: suitability for learning objectives, relevance to subject matter, in accordance with the characteristics of students, in accordance with school conditions and facilities; 2) aspects of practicality, including: ease of use, flexibility, time efficiency, mobility; 3) aspects of effectiveness, including: increasing learning motivation, facilitating understanding of concepts, increasing memory, improving learning outcomes, developing learning media needs to pay attention to existing provisions,

CONCLUSION

The development of Canva-assisted animated video learning media in Pancasila Education for the cultivation and development of honest attitudes, because Canva-assisted learning media is able to accommodate fragments of events in society, provide opportunities for interaction between students, there is room for interpretation of character values, such as: honest attitudes. Thus, learning Pancasila Education in the cultivation and development of honest attitudes needs to develop Canva-assisted learning media because it is more effective and efficient in learning.

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